

Inflammatory markers: An Overview

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Introduction

Inflammation is the body's innate response to injury or insult, including infection, trauma, surgery, burns, and cancer. Certain proteins are released into the bloodstream during inflammation; if their concentrations increase or decrease by at least 25%, they can be used as systemic inflammatory markers. Although there are many inflammatory markers, also known as acute phase reactants, those most commonly measured in clinical practice are C-reactive protein (CRP), erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR), and procalcitonin (PCT). PCT is a newer marker of inflammation that may, in certain cases, identify or exclude bacterial infections and guide antibacterial treatments, because these markers are nonspecific, the tests alone are not diagnostic for a particular condition, but they may help to identify a generalized inflammatory state along with other tests and aid in the differential diagnosis. In some diseases, serial measurements of CRP also may be of prognostic value. Other Inflammatory markers are; Interleukin-6 (IL-6), Interleukin 10 (IL-10), Tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), Monocyte chemoattractant protein 1 (MCP1), C-reactive protein (CRP), Lipoprotein associated to phospholipase A2 (Lp-PLA2), Plasminogen activator inhibitor 1 (PAI-1), Liptine, Cellular adhesion molecule (CAM).

Indications

Aid in the diagnosis of certain suspected inflammatory disorders (eg, ESR is used for giant cell arteritis and CRP for neonatal sepsis). Distinguish between inflammatory and noninflammatory diseases (eg, osteoarthritis versus rheumatoid arthritis or inflammatory bowel disease versus irritable bowel syndrome). Manage certain antibiotic therapies (eg, PCT can be used to support shortening the duration of antimicrobial therapy in patients with lower respiratory tract infections). Predict recovery (eg, PCT can be used to predict 28-day cumulative mortality risk for patients diagnosed with sepsis).

Interleukin- 6 (IL-6)

Interleukin 6 (IL-6) is an interleukin that acts as both a pro-inflammatory cytokine and an anti-inflammatory myokine. In humans, Osteoblasts secrete IL-6 to stimulate osteoclast formation, Smooth muscle cells in the tunica media of many blood vessels also produce IL-6 as a pro-inflammatory cytokine. IL-6's role as an anti-inflammatory myokine is mediated through its inhibitory effects on TNF-alpha and IL-1, and activation of IL-1ra and IL-10.

Functions

IL-6 is an important mediator of fever and of the acute phase response. It is capable of crossing the blood-brain barrier and initiating synthesis of PGE2 in the hypothalamus, thereby changing the body's temperature setpoint. In muscle and fatty tissue, IL-6 stimulates energy mobilization that leads to increased body temperature. IL-6 can be secreted by macrophages in response to specific microbial molecules, referred to as pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs). These PAMPs bind to an important group of detection molecules of the innate immune system, called pattern recognition receptors (PRRs), including Toll-like receptors (TLRs). These are present on the cell surface and intracellular compartments and induce intracellular signaling cascades that give rise to inflammatory cytokine production. Inhibitors of IL-6 (including estrogen) are used to treat postmenopausal osteoporosis. IL-6 is also produced by adipocytes and is thought to be a reason why obese individuals have higher endogenous levels of CRP. Intranasally administered IL-6 has been shown to improve sleep-associated consolidation of emotional memories. IL-6 is responsible for stimulating acute phase protein synthesis, as well as the production of neutrophils in the bone marrow. It supports the growth of B cells and is antagonistic to regulatory T cells. When psychologically stressed, the human body produces stress hormones like cortisol, which are able to trigger interleukin-6 release into the circulation.

Role in diseases

IL-6 stimulates the inflammatory and auto-immune processes in many diseases such as diabetes, atherosclerosis, depression, Alzheimer's Disease, multiple myeloma, prostate cancer, and rheumatoid arthritis.

Tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF α)

Tumor necrosis factor (TNF, cachexin, or cachectin; once named as tumor necrosis factor alpha or TNF α) is a cell signaling protein (cytokine) involved in systemic inflammation and is one of the cytokines that make up the acute phase reaction. It is produced chiefly by activated macrophages, although it can be produced by many other cell types such as CD4+ lymphocytes, NK cells, neutrophils, mast cells, eosinophils, and neurons. TNF is a member of the TNF superfamily, consisting of various transmembrane proteins with a homologous TNF domain. The primary role of TNF is in the regulation of immune cells.

TNF, being an endogenous pyrogen, is able to induce fever, apoptotic cell death, cachexia, inflammation and to inhibit tumorigenesis and viral replication and respond to sepsis via IL1- & IL6-producing cells. Dysregulation of TNF production has been implicated in a variety of human diseases including Alzheimer's, cancer, major depression, psoriasis and inflammatory bowel disease (IBD).

Cell signaling

TNF can bind two receptors, TNFR1 (TNF receptor type 1) and TNFR2 (TNF receptor type 2). TNFR1 is 55-kDa and TNFR2 is 75-kDa. TNFR1 is expressed in most tissues, and can be fully activated by both the membrane-bound and soluble trimeric forms of TNF, whereas TNFR2 is found typically in cells of the immune system, and respond to the membrane-bound form of the TNF homotrimer.

Production

TNF was thought to be produced primarily by macrophages, but it is produced also by a broad variety of cell types including lymphoid cells, mast cells, endothelial cells, cardiac myocytes, adipose tissue, fibroblasts, and neurons. Large amounts of TNF are released in response to lipopolysaccharide, other bacterial products, and Interleukin-1 (IL-1). In the skin, mast cells appear to be the predominant source of pre-formed TNF, which can be released upon inflammatory stimulus (e.g., LPS).

Action

It has a number of actions on various organ systems, generally together with IL-1 and Interleukin-6 (IL-6):

On the hypothalamus:

- Stimulation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis by stimulating the release of corticotropin releasing hormone (CRH).
- Suppressing appetite.
- Fever.

On the liver

- Stimulating the acute phase response, leading to an increase in C-reactive protein and a number of other mediators. It also induces insulin resistance by promoting serine-phosphorylation of insulin receptor substrate-1 (IRS-1), which impairs insulin signaling.
- It is a potent chemoattractant for neutrophils, and promotes the expression of adhesion molecules on endothelial cells, helping neutrophils migrate.
- On macrophages:
- Stimulates phagocytosis, and production of IL-1 oxidants and the inflammatory lipid Prostaglandin E2 (PGE2)

On other tissues

- Increasing insulin resistance. TNF phosphorylates insulin receptor serine residues, blocking signal transduction.

On metabolism and food intake

- Regulates bitter taste perception.
- A local increase in concentration of TNF will cause the cardinal signs of Inflammation to occur: heat, swelling, redness, pain and loss of function.
- Whereas high concentrations of TNF induce shock-like symptoms, the prolonged exposure to low concentrations of TNF can result in cachexia, a wasting syndrome. This can be found, for example, in cancer patients.

C-reactive protein (CRP)

C-reactive protein (CRP) is an annular (ring-shaped), pentameric protein found in blood plasma, whose circulating concentrations rise in response to inflammation. It is an acute-phase protein of hepatic origin that increases following interleukin-6 secretion by macrophages and T cells. Its physiological role is to bind to Lys phosphatidylcholine expressed on the surface of dead or dying cells (and some types of bacteria) in order to activate the complement system. CRP is synthesized by the liver in response to factors released by macrophages and fat cells (adipocytes). It is a member of the pentraxin family of proteins. It is not related to C-peptide (insulin) or protein C (blood coagulation). C-reactive protein was the first pattern recognition receptor (PRR) to be identified.

Function

CRP binds to the phosphocholine expressed on the surface of dead or dying cells and some bacteria. This activates the complement system, promoting phagocytosis by macrophages, which clears necrotic and apoptotic cells and bacteria. This so-called acute phase response occurs as a result of increasing concentrations of IL-6, which is produced by macrophages as well as adipocytes in response to a wide range of acute and chronic inflammatory conditions such as bacterial, viral, or fungal infections; rheumatic and other inflammatory diseases; malignancy; and tissue injury and necrosis. These conditions cause release of interleukin-6 and other cytokines that trigger the synthesis of CRP and fibrinogen by the liver. CRP binds to phosphocholine on micro-organisms. It is thought to assist in complement binding to foreign and damaged cells and enhances phagocytosis by macrophages (opsonin-mediated phagocytosis), which express a receptor for CRP. It plays a role in innate immunity as an early defence system against infections.

Diagnostic use

CRP is used mainly as an inflammation marker. Apart from liver failure, there are few known

factors that interfere with CRP production. Interferon alpha inhibits CRP production from liver cells which may explain the relatively low levels of CRP found during viral infections compared to bacterial infections. Measuring and charting CRP values can prove useful in determining disease progress or the effectiveness of treatments. ELISA, immunoturbidimetry, nephelometry, rapid immunodiffusion, and visual agglutination are all methods used to measure CRP. The risk of developing cardiovascular disease is quantified as follows:

- low: hs-CRP level under 1.0 mg/L
- average: between 1.0 and 3.0 mg/L
- high: above 3.0 mg/L

Normal levels increase with aging, Higher levels are found in late pregnant women, mild inflammation and viral infections (10–40 mg/L), active inflammation, bacterial infection (40–200 mg/L), severe bacterial infections and burns (>200 mg/L). CRP is a more sensitive and accurate reflection of the acute phase response than the ESR (Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate). ESR may be normal while CRP is elevated. CRP returns to normal more quickly than ESR in response to therapy.

References

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/C-reactive_protein#cite_note-pmid22035340-52

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Interleukin_6

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tumor_necrosis_factorhttps://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tumor_necrosis_factor

